
INTERNET AND ITS APPLICATIONS: THE USAGE AMONG POSTGRADUATE STUDENTS

Manjunatha G.¹ & Prof. B. T. Sampath Kumar²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Studies and Research in Library and Information Science, Tumkur University, Tumakuru, Karnataka

² Professor, Department of Studies and Research in Library and Information Science Tumkur University, Tumakuru, Karnataka

Corresponding Author - Manjunatha G.

Email-manjudurga10@gmail.com

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Abstract:

One of the most visible elements of Information and Communication Technology is the Internet. Information can be gathered, stored and disseminated across all academic disciplines. In this paper, the use of the Internet and awareness of the various Internet applications among the Postgraduate students are examined. A questionnaire was used to collect the data from the Post-Graduate Library and Information Science students in selected universities of Karnataka state. In the present study, 67.6% of the students used Internet for searching the information and chatting (54.9%). The study identified that 90.1% of students always used Google chrome and Internet explorer (34.5%). The study also found that most of the students used Internet regularly.

Keywords: *Internet and its applications, Postgraduate students and Karnataka.*

Introduction:

The Internet revolution led to a new generation of college students, where most of them grew with this technology. A large number of people around the world have access to Internet resources, which ensure public, cooperative, and self-sustaining access to information (Culver, 2009). In the education point of view students use Internet for the purpose of downloading e-books, reading scientific articles, asking questions for experts in the online forums and write e-mails, blogs and share knowledge to others (Meti, 2014). The students use internet for their academic and learning. The Internet has been raised tremendously as a platform of communication among the young

generation. Use of the Internet and social media has both positive and negative impact on students' social life. Internet is used for communication and news updates. Sometimes heavy use of the Internet leads to waste of time and depression among students. Use of the Internet and social media lead to healthy life and enrich learning practice (Saha, & Guha, 2019).

In this context, this study has been undertaken to know the use of Internet and its applications by university students.

Research Questions:

The main objectives of the study are to explore the awareness and use of Internet and its applications by students.

Besides this, an attempt is made to find the answer to the following questions:

- For what purpose do the students use Internet and its applications?
- Are they aware and use various Internet applications?
- Are they aware and use of web designing software tools?
- How frequently do they use different kinds of Web browsers?
- Whether they are aware and use of several Web domains?

Hypotheses:

The following hypotheses are formulated:

- There is an association between gender and frequency of use of Internet.

- There is an association between gender and the purpose of use of Internet.

Scope and Methodology:

The scope of the study is confined to only the Students of Library and Information Science students in selected universities in Karnataka state (Table 1). A structured questionnaire was designed to gather the data from the students to fulfill the stated research questions. To get the data from students, the researcher personally visited and distributed questionnaires to the students in selected universities. The duly filled questionnaires were collected from the students and data were coded in the SPSS (Version 26.0) package and analyzed with suitable statistical tests.

Table-1: Sample Size from the Universities

Name of the Universities	No. of respondents	Percentage
Akkamahadevi Women's University, Vijayapura	09	6.3
Bangalore University, Bengaluru	31	21.8
Bengaluru North University, Kolar	12	8.5
Karnatak University, Dharwad	15	10.6
Kuvempu University, Shivamogga	13	9.2
Mangalore University, Mangaluru	11	7.7
Rani Channamma University, Belagavi	09	6.3
Tumkur University, Tumakuru	10	7.0
University of Mysore, Mysuru	26	18.3
Vijayanagara Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Ballari,	06	4.2
Total	142	100.0

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Demographic characteristics of the respondents:

Table-2: Demographic characteristics of the respondents

Demographic of respondents (N=142)	No. of respondents	Percentage	
Gender	Male	49	34.5
	Female	93	65.5
Social Background	Rural	126	88.7
	Urban	16	11.3
Total	142	100	

Table 2 summarizes the demographic characteristics of respondents. It can be seen from this table 65.5% of respondents are female,

while 34.5% are male. The table also shows that 88.7% of students are from rural backgrounds and 11.3% of students are from urban backgrounds. It is noticed

that most students are from rural areas and comparatively more girls have shown keen

Interest to join the LIS course in the selected universities of Karnataka State.

Frequency of use of Internet:

Table-3: Frequency of use of Internet

Frequency	No. of respondents	Percentage
Everyday	134	94.4
2-3 days in week	5	3.5
Once in month	1	0.7
Occasionally	2	1.4
Total	142	100.0

The frequency of Internet use by students is shown in table-3. The majority of students used Internet every day (94.4%) followed by two-three times a week (3.5%). This table also shows that the highest number of respondents are familiar with Internet. To know the

association between gender and frequency of use of Internet, the Chi-square test has been applied. The result indicates that there is no association between gender and frequency of use of Internet ($X^2=4.440$, $DF=3$, $p=.218$). Therefore hypothesis-1 is rejected.

Purpose of Use of Internet:

Table-4: Purpose of Use of Internet

Purpose	Always	Often	Some times	Rarely	Never	Mean	SD	t-tests	P value
To read e-books/e-journals	46 (32.4)	35 (24.6)	52 (36.6)	7 (4.9)	2 (1.4)	3.82	.994	-.005	.996
To read newspapers/ magazines	44 (31)	32 (22.5)	49 (34.5)	14 (9.9)	3 (2.1)	3.70	1.077	1.422	.158
To prepare class notes	52 (36.6)	39 (27.5)	38 (26.8)	10 (7)	3 (2.1)	3.89	1.050	-2.800	.006
To search information	96 (67.6)	24 (16.9)	20 (14.1)	2 (1.4)	00	4.51	.788	.262	.794
To attend online classes	39 (27.5)	27 (19)	55 (38.7)	19 (13.4)	2 (1.4)	3.58	1.074	-2.405	.018
To attend webinars	27 (19)	20 (14.1)	42 (29.6)	35 (24.6)	18 (12.7)	3.02	1.291	-1.623	.107
To send/read e-mails.	61 (43)	31 (21.8)	31 (21.8)	12 (8.5)	7 (4.9)	3.89	1.195	-.938	.351
To watch academic videos (MOOCs)	33 (23.2)	25 (17.6)	44 (31)	19 (13.4)	21 (14.8)	3.21	1.341	-.439	.662
For chatting	78 (54.9)	25 (17.6)	34 (23.9)	2 (1.4)	3 (2.1)	4.22	.997	-.317	.752
To use social networks	77 (54.2)	22 (15.5)	32 (22.5)	8 (5.6)	3 (2.1)	4.14	1.082	.703	.483
For online banking	57 (40.1)	26 (18.3)	36 (25.4)	13 (9.2)	10 (7)	3.75	1.267	-.856	.394
To listen /download music	56 (39.4)	25 (17.6)	35 (24.6)	21 (14.8)	5 (3.5)	3.75	1.223	-.398	.692
To download software games, film, images.	49 (34.5)	34 (23.9)	23 (16.2)	23 (16.2)	13 (9.2)	3.58	1.349	.612	.542

The use of Internet for specific purposes is shown in table-4. The present study found that the majority of the respondents always used Internet to search the information (67.6%), followed by for chatting (54.9%), to use social networks(54.2%), and to send/read e-mails.(43%). Furthermore, the students opined that they used Internet for online banking(40.1%) and very few respondents opined that they use Internet for to attend the webinars(19%).Study also found that

most of the students used the Internet for academic purposes and students used the Internet for other purposes such as to listen /download music, to download software games, film, images etc. There is no significant difference between gender of the respondents except for the variables viz., to prepare class notes ($t = -2.800$, $p = .006$) and to attend online classes ($t = -2.405$, $p = .018$). Hence the Hypotheses -2 has been rejected.

Awareness and use of Internet applications:**Table-5: Awareness and use of Internet applications**

Internet Applications	Aware	Aware and use	Not aware
Google drive	48 (33.8)	93 (65.5)	1 (0.7)
Google translate	46 (32.4)	93 (65.5)	3 (2.1)
Google docs	53 (37.3)	82 (57.7)	7 (4.9)
Google sheet	57 (40.1)	66 (46.5)	19 (13.4)
Google forms	41 (28.9)	86 (60.6)	15 (10.6)
File converter	46 (32.4)	75 (52.8)	21 (14.8)

Table-5 indicates the awareness and use of various Internet application by students. The present study found that the majority of the students are aware and use

Google drive (65.5%) followed by Google translate (65.5%). Less number of students are aware of Google forms (28.9%).

Awareness and use of various Web designing tools**Table-6: Awareness and use of various Web designing tools**

Web designing tools	Aware	Aware and use	Not aware
WordPress	68 (47.9)	34 (23.9)	40 (28.2)
Wix	45 (31.7)	15 (10.6)	82 (57.7)
Weebly	36 (25.4)	16 (11.3)	90 (63.4)
Webflow	35 (24.6)	24 (16.9)	83 (58.5)
Adobe dreamweaver	47 (33.1)	31 (21.8)	64 (45.1)
Google web designer	48 (33.8)	32 (22.5)	62 (43.7)

The awareness and use of various Web designing tools are presented in table-6. It is found that the majority of the

students are aware of Web designing tools like WordPress (47.9%) and Google web designer (20.7%).

Frequency of use of Web browser:**Table 7: Frequency of use of Web browser**

Web Browsers	Always	Often	Some times	Rarely	Never
Google Chrome	128 (90.1)	8 (5.6)	6 (4.20)	0	0
Mozilla Firefox	39 (27.5)	33 (23.2)	30 (21.1)	14 (9.9)	26 (18.3)
Internet Explorer	49 (34.5)	31 (21.8)	40 (28.2)	9 (6.3)	13 (9.2)
Safari Web Browser	22 (15.5)	14 (9.9)	34 (23.9)	29 (20.4)	43 (30.3)
UC Browser	31 (21.8)	24 (16.9)	36 (25.4)	25 (17.6)	26 (18.3)
Opera Web Browser	27 (19)	17 (12)	27 (19)	27 (19)	44 (31)
Netscape Browser	11 (7.7)	9 (6.3)	26 (18.3)	24 (16.9)	72 (50.7)

Frequency of use of web browsers by post graduate students is presented in table 7. The present study found that the majority of the students used Google chrome always (90.1%) followed by

Internet explorer (34.5%). A very small number of students used Netscape browser (7.7%).The table also shows that Google Chrome and Internet Explorer are the most

commonly used browsers for accessing the internet.

Awareness and use of Web domains:

Table-8: Awareness and use of Web domains

Web Domains	Aware	Aware and use	Not aware
.com /.co	48 (33.8)	88 (62)	6 (4.2)
.edu	51 (35.9)	78 (54.9)	13 (9.2)
.org	45 (31.7)	79 (55.6)	18 (12.7)
.ac	42 (29.6)	71 (50)	28 (19.7)
.gov	45 (31.7)	80 (56.3)	17 (12)
.net	51 (35.9)	79 (55.6)	12 (8.5)
.ernet	58 (40.8)	41 (28.9)	43 (30.3)
.mil	50 (35.2)	51 (35.9)	41 (28.9)
.info	48 (33.8)	55 (38.7)	39 (27.5)

Awareness and use of Web domains among the students is presented in table 8. The present study found that the majority of the students are aware and use

of .com/.co (62%) followed by .gov (56.3%). The majority of the students are aware of .ernet (40.8%).

Discussion and Conclusion:

The study explored various interesting findings about the frequency and purpose of using the Internet. 94.4 % of the respondents used the Internet every day to search for information (67.6 %). Many of the students are not familiar with Web designing tools and web domains. As students of Library and Information Science, the students need to know and understand Web designing tools and web domains. The students are very much aware and use web browsers, viz Google Chrome and Internet explorer.

The university need to arrange training programs to orientate the students. Elements on basic and advanced techniques need to be included in the curriculum. Faculty members need to encourage Internet usage among students. The syllabus needs to be revised at least three years once to accommodate the latest technologies. Further, the faculty members need to introduce practical classes to teach Internet applications to the students of Library and Information Science.

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